

**EVALUATION OF EUROBANK EFG BANK DEVELOPMENT PRIORITIES USING
NORMATIVE FORECASTING**

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Abstract: *This paper presents the development and implementation of a normative, quantitative goal oriented technique - PATTERN. The model PATTERN is developed by authors to whom the performance improvement is set as the main goal, while managers at the top and middle managerial positions at Eurobank EFG were in the role of experts. The results of this paper show that PATTERN method needs to be considered for further professional development in all business areas, since it provides more objectivity within the decision making in long-term planning within a complex business environment. Besides contribution to science, this quantitative technique can have practical implementation in all industries.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Assessing future events is an important concern for managers in fast changing environment that becomes more significant than ever before. All we know about the future is uncertainty that poses new and various challenges. In order to mitigate the uncertainty in the process of achieving the company's strategic objectives, forecasting plays a vital role to executives in all industries. Numerous forecasting techniques have been developed to support managers in obtaining predictions and decision makings. Effective forecasting takes into account its critical role in obtaining opinions in different functional areas, each contributing applicable insights and information in order to improve overall accuracy in decision making [1].

The decision making is crucial for managers at all levels in all industries, since decisions may have significant impact on the business. It has a more complex role on different levels of prioritization that has to be taken into consideration in every day decision making process. For successful accomplishment in determining strategic objectives, forecasts play important management concern. Decision making process includes distinct criteria and sub-criteria in order to rank the alternatives of the decision. With respect to the criteria and / or sub-criteria, priorities should be evaluated taking into account a higher goal that leads to the final goal [2]. In practice it is common to use a mix of forecasting techniques that aims to minimize the forecast error [3]. For the managers it is significantly important to examine the data from various perspectives before making decisions.

This paper focuses on the goal oriented, quantitative forecasting method, Planning Assistance through Technical Evaluation of Relevance Numbers, hereafter PATTERN, the supportive tool in prioritization evolution of the goals and sub-goals developed by the authors. PATTERN method was implemented in Eurobank EFG, where the managers at the top and middle of managerial levels of the bank were in the role of experts. The experts who participated in the research were:

1. **Head of Household Lending Division, Mr. Nikolaos Koulompouros**, responsible for business strategy of private individual financing and services, business performance, sales and development. Moreover, Mr. Koulompouros is managing directly and indirectly over 200 employees, who are a part of numerous sectors such as Sales, Risk, Credit, Operations, Product Development, Cards, and Customer Care.
2. **Head of IT, Mr. Milos Pavlovic**, responsible for IT governance and organization related to budgeting and financial monitoring, implementation and monitoring of IT policies and procedures, management reporting, system availability and security, system improvements, projects' monitoring along with managing over 50 employees.
3. **Head of Products, Mr. Nemanja Petrovic**, responsible for managing Product Development

sector with major focus on developing retail lending products and services, managing products portfolio and products life cycle, organizing commercial and marketing activities with the scope of increasing performance of portfolio and overall sales.

The results shows that PATTERN can be a successful and useful tool in business decision making providing more objectivity within certain decision processes in complex business environment. Moreover, taking into account that future is closely related to uncertainty, PATTERN can be a helpful tool in a long-term planning process in order to achieve predefined strategic objectives of a company.

2. GENERAL INSIGHT OF FORECASTING IMPORTANCE

The powerful force of globalization has made business environment very dynamic and challenging for each organization that competes at the market considering the trend of "acceleration" [4]. In the era of highly competitive environment, fast integration of countries, rapid growth of information technologies and electronic communication, technology and innovation play a vital role [5]. "Forecasting is the process of predicting the future" [6] and represents the constituent part in almost all business industries.

Globalization and rapid technology changes represent two main factors playing the focal role for competitiveness. Under such turbulent environment in which life cycle of products continues to shrink, where discontinuous change in demand is a very common phenomenon and where competition is very strong, organizations can only survive if constantly forecast [7,8].

By technological forecasting, companies may address both the incremental changes for using existing technologies and the long run changes for exploration of new technologies. This would be a good opportunity for the companies to remain or to become leaders in their industries and to ensure the first-mover advantage every time over competitors at the market. Similarly, in the defense sector there is a need to predict the capabilities of the enemies as well as to predict defensive weapons as intimidation and predict newer offensive weapons which would in the future provide the advantage over the enemy [7,8].

In order to achieve the determined targets within specified time frame, to overcome all threats and to take advantage over competitors, forecasting is of significant importance in all industries [7,8]. Manufacturing companies forecast demand for their products in order to plan necessary volumes in raw materials and manpower to support production. Service sector forecasts the number of customers in order to provide adequate staff number. Security analysts forecast financial indicators such as profits, debt ratios and revenues of a company and general trends in financial markets in order to recommend investments. Many companies also take into account economic forecasts before making any decisions on capital investments [6].

According to the survey of World Future Studies Federation, the most of forecasting is done in the US, Japan and Europe, while Eastern Europe, Russia and China also

perform technological forecasting but to some extent. Korean Research Center of Science and Technology and Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology are engaged to support forecasting mainly in domain of Information Technology [8].

3. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PATTERN METHOD

Forecasting methods may be divided into two broad groups: exploratory and normative methods [5,12,13]. The exploratory ones deal with the questions of what may, might or could possibly happen on the bases of current information [9,10,11,12,13]. This approach starts from the present conditions, uses data from the past and forecasts the future. Exploratory forecasting includes methods such as Delphi, case study and growth curves methods [9,12,13,15,16].

Normative forecasting is goal-oriented i.e. it reflects the needs of an organization. It deals with the question: "How would we like the future to evolve?" This type of forecasting method takes into account the purpose, mission and most importantly expected achievements in the future of the organization. The question addressed by the normative method is: "What should we do?" [9,10,11,12,13]. Hence, this is a method based on the future needs, yet it forecasts the available capabilities with the assumption that the needs will be achieved. It is an important component of decision making usually associated with large organizations [9,10,11,12,13]. Normative forecasting technique is based on the methods of system analysis [5], where long-term objectives are specified and short-term goals are indicated, strategic alternatives are analyzed to choose the best solution, while resources are mobilized and organized in order to achieve the predefined goals [7]. This forecasting approach includes the scenario writing and relevance trees method [13]. The relevance tree method involves a tree diagrams, hierarchically structuring the sequence of problems that should be solved in order to meet the predefined goal. As prerequisites for using the relevance tree, related factors have to be known [13,14,15,16].

This paper focuses on the normative forecasting technique – PATTERN. Long-term future has always been of interest to institutions, organizations and governments. Systematic, comprehensive, and public aspects—public, in this case, meaning open to examination and review by people other than the planners and forecasters themselves are the key elements that separate the normative forecasting from other kinds of speculations of goals. The normative forecast consists of two important parts i.e. the statement of a goal or set of goals for a specific time and the analysis in detail of how to reach the goal [9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16].

PATTERN is a normative forecasting technique based on relevance tree structure and goal-oriented forecasting method "where one establishes future needs and recedes backwards to the present and to the technologies needed to achieve the objective of the future" [7]. A relevance tree is developed to define and evaluate the alternatives systematically as a tool with which companies' objectives or missions could be achieved [17]. This method has been initially used by the military and space science Honeywell Company for, medical and space purposes [5].

PATTERN, as a quantitative technique, provides support in long term planning giving numerical ranking that provides help in predicting which of the projects is most likely to be realized, assuming that the chosen one is the most beneficial according to the predefined goal [5].

Steps used for PATTERN method are as follows:

- Model description
- Criteria recognition
- Relevance numbers definition
- Data processing and final results [5].

The basic principle of PATTERN is decomposition of the complex problems into easier components and essential advantages of using this method are:

- Possible dynamic adjustments of the plans, including data changes as well as expert team assessment changes;
- Usage of valuable knowledge and experience of experts engaged in forecasting;
- Overcoming the issue of insufficient experts' connectivity of different profiles;
- Method is very efficient due to the quantitative expression of opinions of experts;
- Achieving a considerable degree of objectivity in opinion;
- Revealing the essential scientific issues which may be of high importance for the nation at all;
- Possibility of planning the needs for employees in companies;
- Cost and resource estimation that are required for the project implementation may be obtained, as well as possibility of making an optimal selection of projects that should be realized;
- Groups of experts from various disciplines may be better organized;
- Possibility of analyzing the scientific interests of various institutions, subjects and levels [5];

Despite many advantages that PATTERN method has, there are also some disadvantages such as:

- Individual assessments that influence the scenario and outcome;
- There are no logical elements in the PATTERN method based on which the control mechanism could be established on the whole complex of researches and experiments;
- Use of other methods, such as Delphi method, may prolong the process in some specific cases [5];

However, the PATTERN tool represents the significant contribution of normative forecasting methodology to the development of science and technology [5] with the purpose to be a useful supportive tool for large companies in the planning process during decision making.

4. AN OVERALL EUROBANK EFG INSIGHT IN SERBIA

Since 2000, the banking system started to restore intensively in Serbia after the crash during 90s. The EU-based banks emerged as leaders on the market [18]. Since 2001, The World Bank has played a critical role in reforming Serbia's banking and public finance, education, energy and social sectors, by assisting in developing a more effective business environment. "The World Bank is supporting Serbia to make progress toward full European integration and promoting dynamic economic growth through the accelerated implementation of economic reforms, increasing employment and living standards, and promoting balanced regional development" [19].

As the result, the process of introducing new products and services along with new technologies in the banking sector has grown incredibly. One of the banks that successfully compete in the Serbian market is Eurobank EFG.

Eurobank EFG is a European banking organization, offering a variety of services in the banking sector, including asset management, insurance and other related services in the Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe, Great Britain and Luxembourg. In 2010 Eurobank EFG total assets reached €81.9bn. Eurobank EFG is a member of Eurobank EFG Group, an international banking group, operating in more than 40 countries [20].

Entering the Serbian market, Eurobank EFG has been more concerned with learning about banking markets, selecting an appropriate arena to compete, and determining how to leverage core competencies in the banking market. From the beginning, Eurobank EFG has started to build a leading position in the market, by establishing a strong local presence with the focus on satisfying customers' needs, developing the core products and core competencies.

At present, Eurobank EFG operates through a large network of branches throughout Serbia, offering a variety of standard and innovative banking products to its clients. Furthermore, it preserves one of the leading positions in the most dynamic segments of the banking business i.e. in Small Business, Mortgage and Consumer Loans, Credit Cards, Savings and Money market operations. Eurobank EFG's growth was closely followed by investments in technical and operational infrastructure, human capital, as well as in development of modern banking products and services designed to meet customers' needs. According to the annual report, 2010 was marked with successes despite the challenges in business environment and the effects of the global economic crisis, as reflected in the following indicators:

- Rise of 23% in total assets;
- 3rd position on the market regarding total assets and with a market share of 7.1%;
- 3rd bank in total deposits and 4th in total equity;
- Acquired net profit of RSD 2.6 billion;
- 24% increase in gross loan portfolio;

- Significant reduction of impairment charges (22% lower than in 2009), as a result of prudent expansion policy [20].

Since its establishment, Eurobank EFG has had for its goal to have a professional and adequate staff. It implemented advanced selection, provided trainings, evaluation and used reward methods, aware that people are the most valuable asset [21].

5. DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODEL

5.1 Development and presentation the model

The business environment consists of various factors that can improve or downgrade the business development. The elements of business environment such as global, technological, economic, legal and regulatory, social and competitive could affect the organization’s competence to achieve its objectives, to avoid the threats or to take advantage of new opportunities [4].

Performance improvement has been recognized as the key driver for companies’ profitability and sustainable growth in today’s fast changing business environment, which represent the main goal in the hierarchically structured relevance tree presented in Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, the authors have recognized that performance improvement might be achieved through additional investments, product / service development and process development as sub-goals on the second level in the tree. The sub-goals on the third level in the tree are investments in enterprise resource planning system (ERP) and investments in staff; introduction of PayPal and development of existing mobile phone service; introduction of electronic archive and outsourcing of telemarketing activities.

Fig. 1. Developed forecasting model provided by authors

The tree model presented by Figure 1 shows the levels of significance further used for calculations based on enter values by the selected experts. In the text provided bellow are given the elements of the model representing goals and sub-goals on different levels of significance within the tree of the PATTERN method, as well as the criteria for the second and third level that experts have to take into consideration while making decisions through prioritizing goals.

The criteria at the second level are: costs, time required and impact on profit, while the criteria at the third level are: costs, impact on profit and impact on quality.

LEVEL 1:

A – Performance improvement: Increasing efficiency along with effectiveness leads to the final goal of the

company: profit maximization. Performance improvement could be achieved through: additional investments, product / service development and process development.

LEVEL 2:

B – Additional investments: Additional investments refer to investments in introduction of enterprise resource planning system (ERP) and investment in staff.

C – Product / Service development: Product / Service could be developed through: introduction of a new service – PayPal and improvement of the existing SMS service.

D – Process development: Process development could be achieved through introducing the electronic archive and or outsourcing telemarketing activities.

LEVEL 3:

E - Introduction of Enterprise resource planning system (ERP): By introducing the ERP system, internal and external management information could be integrated into one system across the entire organization. The purpose of ERP is to alleviate the flow of information inside the organization and to manage the connections with the all stakeholders [22].

F- Investment in staff: Eurobank EFG has recognized that employees are the most valuable resource and is committed to the provision of staff development and training opportunities for all. The bank seeks to create an identifiable link between staff development needs and the objectives of the company. Eurobank EFG is committed to the principles of being a recognized investor in staff and seeks consistently to improve the development standards for employees within these principles [21]. Hence, additional investment in staff consists of various trainings, coaching, seminars, according to the needs and the position of the employee.

G - Introduction of a new service – PayPal: There is a great interest in the enabling of PayPal system in Serbia, while legal preconditions are already secured [23]. Smooth functioning of this system would be beneficial both for the customer and for the bank.

H - Improvement of the existing SMS service: Currently, SMS is excellent approach to provide all important information to customers. By enabling payment via SMS using mobile phones, instead of current ways such as e-banking, branch, APS, customers and the bank would benefit first and foremost as this service would be less time consuming for both parties, moreover, opportunity costs are related to branch activities e.g. focus on selling the products.

I - Introducing an electronic archive: Bank generates huge number of documents in paper format. Researches show that one of the biggest hidden costs for the companies is documentation and managing documentation that are kept in paper format. By introducing electronic archive through document management system, bank may decrease costs for employees’ time spent on that particular task, cost for traditional way of archiving – paper costs and costs for the storage of paper documents. Moreover, levels of security might be improved with such innovation [24].

J – Outsourcing of telemarketing activities: Outsourcing of telemarketing activities would have several benefits for the bank such as time saving, focus on core activities, quality improvement, cost reduction, increase speed to market, foster innovation.

Based on the developed model consisting of goals and sub-goals on three levels of significance, as well as the criteria on the second and the third level of the tree of significance, we will implement the PATTERN method using the standard implementation techniques for the PATTERN method described in section 5.2 Implementation of the PATTERN method.

5.2 Implementation of the PATTERN method

Implementation of the PATTERN method consists of determining the significance of the defined goals in relation to the established criteria by the managers of Eurobank EFG, who are in the role of experts, establishing the appropriate weighting coefficients according to the importance of each criterion for all others.

Based on the significance and assessment of the experts, the primary matrices are formed for each case from which the final primary matrices on the second and third level of the tree of significance in this model are gained. On the basis of the final primary matrix the secondary matrix is formed, which as the last type, contains the local numbers of significance for individual topics of the *i*-th level.

In order to understand the basic elements of the PATTERN method, the basic principal terms of the primary matrix are provided below:

Table 1. Primary Matrix [5]

Criteria	α	β	x	v
Weights	W_α	W_β	W_x	W_v
Goals	Contribution marks of goals to criteria – Element weights					
A	S_A^α	S_A^β	S_A^x	S_A^v
B	S_B^α	S_B^β	S_B^x	S_B^v
C	S_C^α	S_C^β	S_C^x	S_C^v
....
j	S_j^α	S_j^β	S_j^x	S_j^v
....
N	S_N^α	S_N^β	S_N^x	S_N^v

- Goals: A, B, C...j...N
- Levels: 1, 2, 3...i...n
- Criteria: $\alpha, \beta, \dots, x, \dots, v$ and $\alpha 1, \beta 1, \dots, x 1, \dots, v 1$
- Criteria weights: $W_\alpha, W_\beta, \dots, W_x, \dots, W_v$ and $W_{\alpha 1}, W_{\beta 1}, \dots, W_{x 1}, \dots, W_{v 1}$
- Contribution marks of the goal j to criteria x - element weights: $S_{j\alpha}, S_{j\beta}, \dots, S_{jx}, \dots, S_{jv}$

The elements of the primary matrices as well as of the final primary matrix, the following specified conditions must be met: [5].

- Sum of criteria weights is 1:

$$\sum_{x=\alpha}^v W_x = 1 \tag{1}$$

- Sum of contribution marks of goals to each criteria is 1:

$$\sum_{j=A}^N S_j^x = 1 \tag{2}$$

- Partial relevance numbers (relevance of goal j for criteria x):

$$PRN_j^x = W_x \cdot S_j^x \tag{3}$$

- Local relevance numbers (relevance of goal j at level i):

$$r_i^j = \sum_{x=\alpha}^v W_x S_j^x \tag{4}$$

- Sum of local relevance numbers at one level has to be 1:

$$\sum_{j=A}^N r_i^j = 1 \tag{5}$$

- Cumulative direct relevance number – Relevance of goal j for main goal, whole relevance tree:

$$R = \prod_{i=1}^n r_i \tag{6}$$

In Table 2 the opinion of the experts at the second level is shown. Considering the criteria and goals at the second level, managers of the Eurobank EFG assigned the element weights calculated in the final primary matrices.

Table 2. Final Primary Matrix at Level 2, provided by authors

Final Primary Matrix at Level 2:			
Criteria	Costs [€]	Time required [h]	Impact on profit [€]
Weights	0.46	0.32	0.22
Goals	Values		
B Additional investments	0.39	0.24	0.32
C Product / Service development	0.30	0.43	0.41
D Process development	0.31	0.32	0.27
Priority at the second level:			
$r_1^C > r_1^B > r_1^D$			
C - B - D			

After the analysis of the criteria weights and sub-goals at the Level 2, it is noticeable that for the performance improvement primary focus and efforts should be given to the product / service development. Additional investments, as factor in achievement of the main company's goal, are at the second place by priority degree, following the product / service development, according to the managers' opinion of the Eurobank EFG. On the other hand, process development is placed on the third level of priority degree. This certainly does not mean that the process development should be neglected, taking into account its relevance in performance improvement.

Next steps show the analysis of the objectives and criteria weights at the Level 3. Moreover, in order to determine more

precisely priorities and comprehensive analysis, it is necessary to compare activities at the Level 3 with the priority degree of objectives at the Level 2. The matrix shown in Table 3 represents the forecasting assessment of managers of the Eurobank EFG for the objectives at Level 3.

Table 3. Final Primary Matrix at Level 3, provided by authors

Final Primary Matrix at Level 3:			
Criteria	Costs [r1]	Impact on profit [r1]	Impact on quality [r1]
Weights	0.39	0.37	0.24
Goals	Values		
E Introduction of Enterprise resource planning system [ERP]	0.07	0.17	0.20
F Investment in staff	0.26	0.16	0.29
G Introduction of new service – PayPal	0.20	0.25	0.07
H Improvement the existing SMS service	0.13	0.15	0.08
I Introducing an electronic archive	0.15	0.17	0.28
J Outsourcing of telemarketing activities	0.19	0.11	0.09

Priority at the third level:
 $r3F > r3I > r3G > r3E > r3J > r3H$
 $F - I - G - E - J - H$

Managers of the bank have recognized that the most important sub-goal is investment in staff, according to the results at the Level 3. Continuing improvement of employees' knowledge and skills are closely associated to the company's objectives, and are beneficial for both parties in short and long run. Following the investments in staff, second priority at third level has the introduction of the electronic archive and focus on cost reduction. According to the managers' opinion, the third place of priorities degree has the introduction of a new service - PayPal. Next, additional investments in ERP system, outsourcing of telemarketing activities and improvement of existing services have the lower priority degree in business performance improvement.

The matrix shown in Table 4 shows the results obtained at the second level in correlation to the results from the third level. The given analysis represents the cumulative results of the performance improvement.

Table 4. Cumulative Matrix, provided by authors

Cumulative Matrix:				
LEVEL 3	r3	LEVEL 2	r2	R
E Introduction of Enterprise resource planning system [ERP]	0.1358	B Additional investments	0.3302	0.0449
F Investment in staff	0.2284	B Additional investments	0.3302	0.0754
G Introduction of new service – PayPal	0.1880	C Product / service development	0.3668	0.0690
H Improvement the existing SMS service	0.1228	C Product / service development	0.3668	0.0450
I Introducing an electronic archive	0.1903	D Process development	0.3030	0.0577
J Outsourcing of telemarketing activities	0.1346	D Process development	0.3030	0.0408

Priority in the cumulative matrix:
 $F - G - I - H - E - J$

According to the experts' opinion, the analysis of the given results in the cumulative matrix shows the highest priority of sub-goals in performance improvement has additional investment in staff, followed by the product / service development through investment in a new service. Next priority goes to process development by introduction of electronic archive and cost reduction, while the improvement of the existing SMS service, introduction of ERP system and outsourcing of telemarketing activities have lower degree of priority in the accomplishment of the main goal.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Effective forecasts have an important role in decision making process by obtaining opinions from different areas. Decision making is a vital part at all managerial levels in all industries since decisions may have significant impact on business. In everyday decision making process, it has a more complex role on various levels of prioritization that has to be taken into account.

The results of the implementation of the PATTERN method, based on determining the significance of the defined goals in relation to the criteria established by the managers of Eurobank EFG, which were in the role of experts, showed that the highest priority in achieving the main goal, i.e. performance improvement, is investing in the human resources through advanced selections, training programs, methods of evaluation and rewards. The managers of Eurobank EFG have estimated that the employees are just the greatest comparative advantage of the Bank. According to the experts another priority in achieving the main goal has the product / service development with the primary focus on investments in new services, i.e. introduction of PayPal, since innovations are the necessity in the era of highly competitive and fast changing environment. The next on the list of priorities is the improvement of the process through the introduction of electronic archives, which would lead to the reduction of operating costs, while development of existing service, introduction of ERP and outsourcing of telemarketing activities have lower degree of priority in the accomplishment of the main goal.

More objectivity can be gained with the use of PATTERN method when making decisions in complex business environment. It can also be of importance in long-term planning in order to achieve the objectives of a company.

Modern decision-making systems require optimization of resources and time. The present model is shown to be interesting for further consideration for various requirements of all business areas. Besides science the PATTERN method can have practical implementation in all industries and it can be applied in combination with exploratory forecasting and other methods.

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